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2 **Is it time to describe new species without diagnoses? - A comment on**
3 **Sharkey *et al.* (2021)**

4

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22 **Running title (short title):** Species without diagnoses?

23

24 **Abstract**

25 New methods in taxonomy and systematics can influence the overall practice of formally
26 naming and describing biodiversity. DNA barcoding has been controversial since its emer-
27 gence, but now, large scale species descriptions exclusively based on barcodes have created
28 what can be called a "new quality of performance". Its limitations are discussed from different
29 perspectives: nomenclature, general pragmatism, and problems of DNA-based species delimita-
30 tion in the light of the central aim of achieving a robust and stable nomenclature of organ-
31 isms, essential for all applications of biodiversity research. This issue needs to be addressed to
32 prevent restraining the progress of taxonomy and its ability to contribute to modern science.

33

34 **Key words.** Taxonomy, species delimitation, *COI* barcoding, nomenclature rules.

35

36 Taxonomy implies two separate processes of knowledge acquisition: 1) referencing speci-
37 mens to an existing system of taxa and their names according to the principle of priority, type
38 specimens, and Linnaean nomenclature (ICZN 1999); and 2) the delimitation of species units.
39 The first step is a procedure that combines archival activity, i.e., considering the previous
40 publication record with the help of the type specimens preserved in natural history collections,
41 and a systematic classification effort based on a phylogeny or shared synapomorphies. The
42 latter involves testing a scientific hypothesis about which specimens are included in a species
43 entity and how to delineate a boundary between this and the most closely related putative tax-
44 on (once more with reference to type specimens if a new species is to be distinguished from a
45 known one). The functionality of this reference system, on the basis of which over 1.5 Mio.
46 valid animal species have been described to date (IUCN 2020), has historically been guaran-
47 teed, despite the existence of a large number of different species concepts (Stankowski &
48 Ravinet 2021), by the existence of one prevailing reference trait complex, i.e., morphology,
49 for all names, and is expressed by the fixation of a physical type specimen (current nomencla-
50 ture rules imply this but do not state it explicitly).

51 Species delimitation methods, along with various species concepts, continue to evolve and
52 improve with new technology, more robust data, and increasingly sophisticated algorithms
53 (de Queiroz 2007). Morphology-based species delimitations (historically performed by
54 trained taxonomists and being sometimes perceived as 'subjective') are being refined by
55 mechanized ('objective') methodologies and new lines of evidence, such as behavior, natural
56 history, morphometric data, genetic data, etc.

57 In a recent paper, Sharkey *et al.* (2021) described 403 hymenopteran species new to science in
58 what they call a “minimalist revision”. Their species descriptions are mostly composed of a
59 nucleotide sequence of the mitochondrial protein-coding gene cytochrome *c* oxidase subunit 1
60 (*COI* or DNA barcode) (accompanied by a simple neighbor-joining tree) and one photograph,
61 rarely more, including collection data and often host data of the preserved type specimens.

62 While taxonomists have long debated standards for species descriptions, that discussion has
63 recently mainly focused on the principle of type specimen preservation (e.g., Amorim *et al.*
64 2016; Ceriaco *et al.* 2016; Krell and Marshall 2017) for which the International Code of Zoo-
65 logical Nomenclature (ICZN 1999, 2017) provides rather clear rules and recommendations. In
66 contrast to this, ICZN recommendations regarding the quality of data used for the delimitation
67 of new taxa are rather general and allow for a wider margin of interpretation: "An author,
68 when drawing up the description of a new nominal taxon, should include comparisons with
69 appropriate related taxa in order to assist later identification of the taxon..." (ICZN 1999: 125

70 [Appendix B]). This is in line with recent demands for more hypothesis-driven research in
71 modern taxonomy (Vences 2020), in which diagnoses should play a major role, to reduce the
72 image of taxonomy as purely descriptive. The majority of new species "descriptions" by
73 Sharkey *et al.* (2021) fail to comply with such a recommendation. The user of such descrip-
74 tions has to search the "diagnosis", either reexamining the type specimens or by reanalysis of
75 the *COI* barcode data. This by itself does not threaten the nomenclatural availability of the
76 names proposed, since Appendix B (ICZN 1999) is a mere recommendation, but their mini-
77 malist approach challenges the criteria of availability of newly established names set by the
78 Code. In fact, Article 13.1.1 (ICZN 1999) states that a criterion of a name's availability is the
79 presence of a "description or definition that states in words characters that are purported to
80 differentiate the taxon". Both "description" and "definition" are also defined in the Code
81 Glossary (an integral mandatory part of the Code, see also art. 89 of the Code). According to
82 the Glossary a "definition" is "a statement in words that purports to give those characters
83 which, in combination, uniquely distinguish a taxon" and a "description" is "a statement in
84 words of taxonomic characters of a specimen or a taxon". It is debatable whether a DNA se-
85 quence alone can fulfil the requirement of being "a statement in words". It could be argued
86 that the letters forming the sequence are the initials of the nucleotide bases, and therefore the
87 DNA sequence is nothing but a list of characters (even if abbreviated, based on a universal
88 convention); others will argue that the sequence does not fulfil the requirements of Art. 13.1.1
89 and therefore deem those names unavailable. This minimalism could therefore become a
90 source of "limbo names", i.e., names which may or may not be considered available, accord-
91 ing to subjective evaluations by different users of taxonomy. The Code of Zoological Nomen-
92 clature needs to become more explicit and should discourage minimalist approaches in a way
93 that such divergent interpretations are no longer possible.

94

95 In the past two decades, DNA barcoding has increased the quality and reproducibility of spe-
96 cies' characterization and enabled rapid assessments of biodiversity (Taberlet *et al.* 2012; Yu
97 *et al.* 2012; DeSalle and Goldstein 2019). A major advantage is the ability to standardize and
98 automate species recognition by using a single gene fragment with standardized protocols
99 (e.g., Carstens *et al.* 2013). DNA sequences such as *COI* barcodes include all the possibly
100 informative characters that they have. The 5'-half of the *COI* gene has been the most widely
101 used marker in animals (Blaxter 2016). DNA-based species delimitation also made way for
102 the direct inference of species boundaries from unknown samples (Pons *et al.* 2006), and al-
103 lowed association of different life stages with each other (Ahrens *et al.* 2007). At an earlier

104 stage of the DNA barcoding campaign, Hebert *et al.* (2004) stated that their results "illustrate
105 the value of DNA barcoding, especially when coupled with traditional taxonomic tools, in
106 disclosing hidden diversity". Others have enthusiastically suggested completely replacing
107 traditional taxonomy by a "DNA taxonomy" (Tautz *et al.* 2003). While in these early years no
108 species were formally described and named according to the Zoological Code exclusively
109 using barcodes (Hebert *et al.* 2004), this happened later (e.g., Brower 2010; Meierotto *et al.*
110 2019; Sharkey *et al.* 2021). In some cases, diagnoses were made specific by highlighting di-
111 agnostic nucleotide positions, and in others, such as Meierotto *et al.* (2019), delimitation was
112 based on threshold clustering (2%) as implemented in the Barcode of Life Index Number
113 (BIN; Ratnasingham and Hebert 2013). In Sharkey *et al.* (2021), most of the descriptions
114 solely authored by Sharkey himself lack any species diagnostics (same applies to Doerder
115 2019); instead, pure nucleotide data (in the case of Doerder 2019 only NCBI accession num-
116 bers) are provided along with neighbor joining trees. These trees, however, do not show quali-
117 tative or diagnostic characters but only reflect genetic distances within an assemblage of taxa
118 of (poorly defined) limited geographical scope.

119

120 Molecular characters, alone or supplemented with other evidence such as ecological or life
121 history data, have been used in the past for describing new species of different organisms that
122 are morphologically extremely similar and the taxonomic distinctiveness of which is not easi-
123 ly diagnosed morphologically (e.g., Brower 2010). Most of these works have also assessed
124 morphological variation, thus providing a link to the existing diagnostic reference system
125 based on morphology (Burns *et al.* 2008; Halt *et al.* 2009; Pfeiler *et al.* 2011). Renner (2016)
126 discussed the use of DNA characters in the formal naming of species based on previous works
127 that used DNA marker information for species diagnosis (of which the majority provided a
128 link to morphological traits in the descriptions). She suggested incorporating DNA barcodes
129 into species diagnoses as a recommendation in all codes of organismal nomenclature.

130

131 Zamani *et al.* (2021) already raised critical arguments against an exclusively DNA-based ap-
132 proach of species description (Meierotto *et al.* 2019), especially regarding the ignorance of
133 previously described species, the pure use of molecular diagnoses, the use of insufficient pho-
134 tographic documentation instead of a "morphological description", and the huge gaps in the
135 existing barcode database, which includes maybe 2% of currently named species worldwide
136 (see <http://www.boldsystems.org/>). These issues alone would be sufficient to make *COI* bar-
137 codes unsuitable as stand-alone reference system for the delineation of new species. Future

138 discussions might also involve environmental DNA as already being the case in fungal taxon-
139 omy (e.g., Ryberg and Nilsson 2018; Hongsanan *et al.* 2018; Wu *et al.* 2019).

140 The approach chosen by Sharkey *et al.* (2021a) is problematic, since it provides neither DNA-
141 based nor morphology-based species diagnoses, i.e., it does not say *how* one species differs
142 from other related ones. This, however, is precisely hypothesis testing in taxonomy, and
143 therefore represents a bedrock of science. Neglecting the recommendations of the ICZN (see
144 above), Sharkey *et al.* (2021a) name species in this limited way for the first time on a large
145 scale. In a reply to Zamani *et al.* (2021) Sharkey *et al.* (2021b) again justified this approach
146 without giving a better rationale than before. If this sets a precedent, we might soon have to
147 cope with two parallel taxonomies, in which long established (morphology-defined) names
148 might become *nomina dubia* (e.g., Pfeiler & Nazario-Yepiz 2020) since reference systems
149 (morphology vs *COI* sequences) for the taxa are not directly and immediately relatable. Such
150 parallel taxonomies that consider the names of the other faction doubtful would be extremely
151 detrimental for taxonomy, a result that most supporters of the current barcoding community
152 would neither like to see nor stand for. Moreover, such a situation would paralyze cautious
153 taxonomists working with morphology because reference systems are not directly compatible
154 and also exclude taxonomists (Dupérré 2020) who do not have access to appropriate funding
155 or resources. The BioScan consortium (Pennisi 2019), for example, seems as yet unconnected
156 to the taxonomic community and its needs (Pinheiro *et al.* 2019).

157

158 Working outside the existing reference system for established taxonomic names would not be
159 the only flaw of a stand-alone-*COI* barcode taxonomy. In the past 15 years, empirical studies
160 of DNA- and integrative taxonomy (e.g., Carstens *et al.* 2013) have demonstrated that DNA
161 taxonomy is far more complex and complicated than the oversimplified assumption that the
162 "barcode gap" will distinguish species (e.g., Meyer & Paulay 2005; Wiemers & Fiedler 2007).
163 This assumption is only the tip of an iceberg of problems. Despite its apparent simplicity and
164 increasing low-cost, *COI* is rather unsuitable for inferring species boundaries due to many
165 issues: species delimitation and identification based on information from a single mitochon-
166 drial gene is prone to errors due to extrachromosomal inheritance and accordingly reduced
167 rate of gene flow, little recombination, incomplete lineage sorting, sex-biased dispersal,
168 asymmetrical introgression, and/or *Wolbachia*-mediated genetic sweeps (Funk & Omland
169 2003; Ballard & Whitlock 2004; Petit & Excoffier 2009; Klopstein *et al.* 2016). Furthermore,
170 coalescence times are three to four times faster than in nuclear markers (Birky *et al.* 1989;
171 Palumbi *et al.* 2001). Thus, divergence in mtDNA may be a result of speciation, or it may not

172 if it is not correlated with evidence from nuclear/genomic DNA. There is certainly some prac-
173 tical convenience in examining environmental samples using a single marker as opposed to
174 multiple markers. Also, costs are currently still lower compared to nuclear multi-marker ap-
175 proaches. Its inaccuracy is due to widely distributed mitochondrial parphyly of species,
176 which increases with geographical upscaling and more extensive sampling of the analyzed
177 data (Bergsten *et al.* 2012), common sex-biased dispersal and thus biased patterns of *COI*
178 divergence as well as ancestral polymorphism leading to false "cryptic" divergence (e.g.,
179 Ahrens *et al.* 2013; Eberle *et al.* 2019). The *COI*-inferred species number may in such cases
180 exceed the true species number by up to ten times (Eberle *et al.* 2019). This level of inaccu-
181 racy is too high to be acceptable for a robust and stable species delimitation and nomenclature.
182 Furthermore, the outcome of species delimitation analyses is affected by (unbalanced) sam-
183 pling, effective population size (of each species), fluctuation of effective population size
184 (within a group of taxa whose species limits are to infer), the depth of phylogenetic sampling,
185 and last but not least, by the choice of sampling or the method of species delimitation (Es-
186 selstyn *et al.* 2012; Fujisawa & Barraclough 2013; Ahrens *et al.* 2016; Meier *et al.* 2021). In
187 short, results of a DNA barcode-based taxonomy are not as objective and stable as widely
188 claimed. Meier *et al.* (2021) also underlined the instability of BINs, on which species entities
189 of Sharkey *et al.* (2021a) were based, and that their circumscription is founded partly on pro-
190 prietary and unpublished data. To uncritically derive conclusions based on DNA data is prob-
191 lematic (Carstens *et al.* 2013; Meier *et al.* 2021); even multi-gene nuclear DNA data may re-
192 sult in over-splitting of true species, although applying current state-of-the-art species delimi-
193 tation methods, like those based on the multispecies coalescent model (e.g., Sukuruman &
194 Knowles 2017).

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196

197 As most of these problems have long been recognized, taxonomists have developed integra-
198 tive taxonomy approaches incorporating both molecular and morphological data (Padiál *et al.*
199 2010; Schlick-Steiner *et al.* 2010; Yeates *et al.* 2011; Eberle *et al.* 2016). While there are
200 many excellent examples of good practice of "turbo taxonomy" using such integrative ap-
201 proaches (e.g., Riedel *et al.* 2013a,b, 2014, 2019; Srivathsan *et al.* 2019), a further step for-
202 ward was achieved by the establishment of integrative taxonomic approaches using iterative
203 analyses (e.g., Solís-Lemus *et al.* 2015). Contrary to the claim that these methods require mul-
204 tiple molecular markers (Sharkey *et al.* 2021a), this approach can also be used with DNA bar-
205 codes and trait measurements (although it benefits from additional markers). Further ap-

206 proaches that are more scalable are being developed (Derkarabetian *et al.* 2019). Such meth-
207 ods combine different sources of evidence such as morphology, multiple nuclear genes, etc. in
208 a single species delimitation analysis, which helps to overcome major philosophical problems
209 in taxonomy through the application of alternative species concepts (Conix 2018). However,
210 most of the highly informative markers of the multi-gene studies have problems in common,
211 either a lack of universality (for a universal reference system such as *COI* barcodes) or a lack
212 of resolution (Eberle *et al.* 2020). This is why *COI* data should and will have a crucial role in
213 species identification and biodiversity monitoring. Recently, however, nuclear markers have
214 been identified that are much more widely applicable and show even better discriminating
215 power than mitochondrial DNA (Eberle *et al.* 2020; Dietz *et al.* 2021). With the ever decreas-
216 ing sequencing costs of genomic data and increasing computational power, these markers
217 might soon be ready to complement *COI* barcodes in the context of a taxonomy in which data
218 for species discovery are inclusive rather than exclusive, and in which the major goal will be
219 the completion of reference data sets (Miralles *et al.* 2020), including morphology, of the en-
220 tirety of global diversity.

221 Sharkey *et al.* (2021a,b) in reply to Zamani *et al.* (2021), are well aware of some of the prob-
222 lems we raise here, but the answers they offer are a combination of postponing the solution or
223 ignoring the problem: parallel taxonomies will persist until other taxonomists can close the
224 gap between the two mutually exclusive reference systems by subsequently documenting the
225 morphology of Sharkey's type specimens. Species exclusively based on *COI* barcodes would
226 dictate a temporary taxonomy as the result of the current opportunities (relying on an outdated
227 methodology (De Salle & Goldstein 2019; Meier *et al.* 2021) and determined by financial
228 constraints. Future taxonomists, likely using emerging and more appropriate genomic data,
229 would have to correct the created taxonomic inflation (Vences 2020) by linking *COI*-based
230 species to those so far only known by morphology by undertaking morphological analysis
231 afresh – a non-trivial task. Taxonomists or ecologists who are not in a position to produce
232 barcodes, cannot test and use the data from Sharkey's species descriptions. Collections with
233 samples suitable for DNA extraction have become more common in the last decades, but of-
234 ten still cover a too limited number of species and geographical areas to allow conclusions
235 about biodiversity in time and space. In contrast, natural history collections still harbor mil-
236 lions of unidentified insect specimens from all over the world (in addition to the type materi-
237 al). To obtain comprehensive biodiversity data in time and space and not only from appropri-
238 ately preserved recent material, these collections will have to continue to be examined based
239 on morphology.

240 Another question concerns the fate of the diagnostic morphological evidence that was elabo-
241 rated in the background of Sharkey's study (Sharkey *et al.* 2021a) and that was used to verify
242 the barcoding databases and to assign the species to the respective genera in order to properly
243 name them. If there is no published record, not even a brief one, of morphological characters
244 in the species diagnosis, then it remains unclear how integration with barcode data, as men-
245 tioned by Sharkey *et al.* (2021a), could be implemented. The knowledge of how to do this is
246 likely to be lost once the specialist, who examined the original type specimens (as outlined by
247 Sharkey *et al.* 2021a), is gone.

248 Morphology-based taxonomy can also be rapid in species discovery (e.g., Fabrizi *et al.* 2019,
249 2021), if at least moderate funding is available. We acknowledge the need for innovative and
250 even unorthodox approaches in largely unknown, megadiverse taxa (Bickel 2009; Meierotto
251 *et al.* 2019; Vences 2020), but we consider the "minimalist" approach of Sharkey *et al.*
252 (2021a) to be more harmful than useful. What is the advantage of naming BIN clusters or mo-
253 lecular operational taxonomic units if it is unclear whether they are species or not (e.g., Brow-
254 er 2010; Blaxter 2016; Vences 2020; Meier *et al.* 2021), and if they are not integrated into the
255 existing reference system? What is the criterion for applying one reference system (morphol-
256 ogy) or another (*COI* sequences), and who makes this decision? We contend that a temporary
257 and parallel taxonomy exclusively based on *COI* barcodes is not a constructive way to face
258 the taxonomic impediment or to guarantee nomenclatural stability in the 21st century. Exam-
259 ples of integrative "turbo taxonomy" (see above) have shown that we can do better. The use
260 of molecular data for species assessments and discovery is only progressive in an integrated
261 framework where new evidence is compatible with existing knowledge, and where competing
262 hypotheses can be tested against each other in a framework of established, widely accepted
263 and clearly specified scientific rules.

264 Adapting scientific processes and hypotheses to the most economic or available methodology
265 and technical feasibility is problematic. Massive innovation from new technologies, such as
266 barcoding, deep learning, or information science, however, should not bring us to a decline in
267 our understanding of species, and in consequence their naming (e.g., Kennedy *et al.* 2005;
268 Garnett *et al.* 2020; Cellinese *et al.* 2021). This would be extremely detrimental to taxonomy
269 as a science. Last but not least, deep learning and automated image recognition (Høye *et al.*
270 2021; Gerovichev *et al.* 2021) provide great potential even in small insects to employ mor-
271 phology in taxonomy and rapid automatized biodiversity assessment, as well as for fast and
272 automatized morphological trait extraction (e.g., Klasen *et al.* 2020). Thus, future biodiversity
273 research will rely on all available diagnostic data (morphology and DNA) for species identifi-

274 cation and delimitation. Therefore, the future of taxonomy will embrace integrative rather
275 than exclusive approaches.

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